

A Hybrid model based on CNN And Wavelet transform for Detecting Respiratory Disorders

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Abstract:

We proposed a novel methodology of Haar wavelet transform for respiratory signal processing. We analyze and implement a Haar transform for separating the frequency bands of respiratory signals.

The architectures were implemented in VHDL language. Our investigation results show that energy-efficient Haar wavelet architecture employs de-noising phase. We implemented Haar wavelet transform based respiratory signal analysis using MATLAB software and we used HDL Coder for MATLAB to VHDL conversion. We are using CNN model for training and for recognition of respiratory disorders. We prove that our method yields better results compared to state-of-art criteria like DWT based respiratory signal processing in terms of metrics like mse, snr, psnr.

Index Terms—Haar, respiratory signal, Wavelet Transform.

I. INTRODUCTION

The basic investigation Signal processing in respiratory illnesses such as cardiac issues, and insomnia are of particular interest to the biomedical of respiratory region. According to studies, respiratory illnesses are very common in the general population [1].

Asserts that proper medical diagnosis depends on the ability to discriminate between normal respiratory (lung) and aberrant noises (such as crackles and wheezes). All the information on the pathology and physiology of lung and airway

A stethoscope is typically used during the examination in low and medium-intensity cases in order to accurately confirm the breathing noises. They can provide crucial hints regarding the location and the pathology's character. Wheeze, rattle, and stridor are the respiratory noises that are most frequently heard in clinical settings [3].

Respiratory symptoms associated with different illnesses normally appear between 63Hz and 500Hz, although they can reach 2,000Hz [4]. This brief uses five major frequencies ranging from 0Hz to 2,000Hz to recognize breathing signals. Analyzing breathing signals is challenging due to signal interference. As a result, we require a noise filter interference reduction device to clear the breath signals, which carry critical information.

Wavelet transform methods have been used in a number of scholarly articles to analyze respiratory signals. To evaluate lung sounds, the majority of them employ Daubechies, Symmlet, or Coiflet wavelet transforms. Wavelet families can be created using the Hole algorithm [9], while preserving their nonlinear character.

However, from a mathematical perspective, Haar family of wavelet transforms is the simplest. We demonstrate how effective frequency bands of respiratory symptoms can be separated using Haar' s decomposition method.

Using multi-level Haar transforms with one levels with ($M = 1$), two levels with ($M = 2$), and three levels with ($M = 3$). The following are our contributions, which are. Included in this brief: - 1.) Identify the frequency ranges of abnormal respiratory signals.

2) Demonstrate effectiveness of Haar-5.

The investigation of respiratory signal processing is fundamental in biomedical area, mainly in respiratory disorders, such as lack of concentration, heart problems and sleeplessness.

The analysis of breathing signals is not an easy task. Since the signal suffers from interference. Therefore, we require a noise filter interference reduction system for clearing the breath signals containing valuable information. Breathing noises are audible sounds associated with breathing.

In low- and medium-intensity cases, the exam usually requires a stethoscope to correctly verify the breathing noises.

II. PREVIOUS METHODOLOGIES

A. Haar wavelet for Respiratory Signal Processing

Due to the presence of cardiac sounds in this frequency range, noise in the low-frequency band (0 to 62.5 Hz) dominates all forms of lung sounds [12]. Therefore, pre-processing and noise removal from lung signals are essential steps prior to signal analysis.

The respiratory signal for lung sounds was obtained at a sampling frequency of 2,000 Hz using the PhysioNet/CinC Challenge 2016 database. The input signal $X(n)$ is split up into five levels of decomposition signals D1 to D5. Wavelets can be used to remove this frequency range (0-62.5Hz). As per reference [13], an electronic stethoscope was utilized to extract the Y-axis of the a0001m respiratory signal from the PhysioNet database. The wavelet coefficients are then extracted using MATLAB software tool. After applying wavelet transform for respiratory signal, signal is decomposed into approximate and detailed coefficients.

The respiratory sound value is represented by amplitude in each of the graphs, with a resolution of 16 bits for 40,000 samples.

The signal noise is concentrated on the approximate portion of the signal (A5). It indicates that noise exists in the approximation coefficient (A5) in the low-frequency band (0– 62.5 Hz), which introduces spuriousness into the analysis of respiratory physiological signals. Consequently,

the five decomposition level wavelet Haar consolidates the signal extraction efficiency in this frequency range. Furthermore, the decomposition levels (D1-D5), a group of frequency bands that cause respiratory illnesses, have been linked to respiratory diseases in the literature [14]– [16] vary from 100Hz to 2,000Hz. Table I confirms that the Haar-5 cover well this frequency range (100 to 2,000Hz).

All of the frequency bands that could potentially have respiratory pathologies or noise, up to and including 15 (D15). To meet the noise band without using the approximation coefficient A5, D6 to D15 would be required. This would result in a significant rise in the quantity of arithmetic operators. Therefore, Table I demonstrates that the respiratory signal can be processed by Haar-5 effectively. Put differently, the Haar-5 produces a signal that is divided into clusters based on the details and approximation coefficients. Given that we know which frequency each decomposition level belongs to, the details can indicate which disease is associated with each decomposition level (D1– D5). Because it matches the pathological frequency and the noise band (as determined by the approximation coefficient A5), the Haar-5 satisfies the application.

The output of the inverse Haar-5 transform of the a0001m signal is displayed. First, using the suggested Haar-5 hardware and the MATLAB co-simulation process, we were able to obtain the decomposition levels and approximation. The signal is then obtained in the time domain by applying the Haar-5 reverse transform. A total of 40,000 signals were sampled at the highest frequency (500MHz) of the proposed Haar-5, requiring 80 μ s to complete the sampling process.

B. MULTI-LEVEL HAAR TRANSFORM

We demonstrate the competitive nature of the $M = 1$ and $M = 2$ levels, which provide a wide range of possibilities for a Haar-5. The Haar transform's processing module (PM) is represented by these levels. These blocks have less critical path (CP) and fewer additions and multiplications than the $M = 3$ level, according to Table II's values. However, Table II demonstrates how difficult it is to

implement a complete Haar with $M = 5$ or even a combination of a $M = 4$ block and a $M = 1$ block. This is mostly because there are a lot of additions and multiplications that must be done.

We presented an investigation to efficiently implement Haar transform architecture with five decomposition levels.

The proposed Haar-5 processes the respiratory signal efficiently since it meets the noise band, the pathological frequency bands robustly.

III PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Here CNN model is used for training and for recognition of disorder signals. Here we are implementing Haar wavelet transform for signal interpretation. Haar wavelet transform decomposes respiratory signal into sub bands. These sub bands are used for analysis of signal.

Since the suggested Haar transform meets both the pathological and noise frequency bands with robustness, it processes the respiratory signal efficiently.

Figure: Block Diagram of proposed methodology

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To assess each solution in terms of circuit area, power dissipation, and energy per operation (EPO), VLSI logic syntheses were carried out in all architectures. Synthesis tool automatically infers, we describe the Haar structures in VHDL.

We are removing base line drift in pre-processing phase. Base line is an electrical signal from a sensor when no measured variable is present, often referred to the output at no-load condition.

Figure: steps followed in proposed scheme

Baseline drift is the low-frequency signal variation that occurs in the baseline due to low-frequency variations in the detector and/or instrument-controlled parameters. Base line drift removal is used in pre-processing phase as noise removing filter. After applying Haar wavelet transform we will get wavelet coefficients of respiratory signal, which are useful to analyze and extract signal features. Based on obtained features, Convolutional neural network is used to classify abnormal signal and normal signal.

We are using MATLAB R2018b software tool for base line drift removal, wavelet transform and CNN model for signal classification then we are converting MATLAB code to VHDL code by using HDL Coder toolbox, which is built in toolbox in MATLAB. We verify our VHDL output results in XILINX VIVADO Software.

Figure 1: Respiratory signal plot

Figure 2: plot of wavelet decomposed signal

Figure 3: Plot related to Magnitude and Phase response of a signal

Figure 4: Power Spectral Density plot of a Signal.

Figure 5: Results of wavelet coefficients obtained using XILINX Vivado software

The Haar wavelet transform is a particularly attractive option when reducing power dissipation is an important design consideration because of its low hardware implementation complexity and ease of use. As shown in Table IV, several works that employ the wavelet transform in the Haar base investigate these characteristics in the widest range of application domains. In [18], a novel algorithm for quickly computing the Haar wavelet transform is presented, along with its potential uses in the waveform's time-frequency analysis. The de-noising filter in [10]. A real-time DWT based signal de-noising algorithm for medical signal preprocessing is introduced in the work in [19]. The wavelet transform has been used to analyze the extraction of respiratory signals.

In order to lower the noise of the collected lung sounds, the work in [5] uses the wavelet method. The literature did not contain any studies that looked into Haar-5 hardware architectures for processing respiratory signals. Nonetheless, we contrast our suggestion with the most recent Haar-5 architectures, which concentrated on separating the noise signals and frequency bands (i.e., related applications). An FPGA based de-noising application solution is demonstrated in the work in [10]. Although it utilizes Haar-5 as well, the work in [10] does not look into the hardware optimization options that we are providing. Table V shows that our best suggestion has a maximum clock frequency that is significantly higher than those of [10] and [19].

Notably, our proposal for an H-IV architecture achieves an EPO of 75.64, which is 1150 times less energy-efficient than the state-of-the-art solutions [19]. We explain these remarkable results by pointing out that the de-noising system of [19], which consists of DWT, thresholding and IDWT, contains blocks that are superfluous for our intended use.

V.CONCLUSION

We presented an investigation to efficiently implement a Haar transform. The proposed Haar-5 processes the respiratory signal efficiently since it meets the noise band and the pathological frequency bands robustly.

Here we are using a signal classification algorithm regarding pathology since we already know the frequency range through Haar with decomposition level 5. We are now integrating baseline drift reduction in our preprocessing step. We are developing a CNN model to detect respiratory disorders. Respiratory signals are obtained from the Physionet database. The CNN model is taught to distinguish between normal and pathological respiratory signals. In future work we are using buzzer, gsm module, gps module to track patient and to get text alert to physician and sounds buzzer to alert nearby people.

VI. REFERENCES

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